

UNVEILING PREDICTORS: E-LEARNING PRACTICES IN NWFP HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS, PAKISTAN

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Abstract: This study investigates the intricate relationship between perceptions, theories, and practices surrounding e-Learning development and utilization in higher education institutions (HEIs). Drawing on insights from Aviram and Tami (2004), it explores how the perceptions and theories of both developers and users serve as predictors of e-Learning practices. Additionally, Sasseville's (2004) assertion that technology-related changes are often viewed through a personal rather than social lens underscores the nuanced nature of integrating e-Learning into educational contexts. At a broader level, contrasting perspectives emerge regarding the role of educational technologies in HEIs: the 'instrumental/supplementary' view versus the 'substantive/liberal' perspective. While the former treats information and communication technologies (ICTs) as technical tools devoid of transformative potential, the latter, advocated by Macleod (2005) and Ezer (2006), posits that ICTs can fundamentally reshape societal culture by their mere existence. Through a comprehensive analysis of these theoretical frameworks, this study aims to elucidate the underlying dynamics shaping e-Learning practices in HEIs, shedding light on the dichotomy between perceiving ICTs as mere instruments versus catalysts for societal change.

Keywords: e-Learning, higher education institutions (HEIs), perceptions, theories, technology integration

INTRODUCTION

The perceptions and theories of developers and users of e-Learning have been used as the predictors of development and use practices of e-Learning in higher education institutions (HEIs) (Aviram and Tami, 2004). Furthermore, technology-related changes are perceived as personal rather than social challenges (Sasseville, 2004). At the broader level, educational technologies are perceived either as 'instrumental/supplementary' or 'substantive/liberal' in higher education. If information and communication technologies (ICTs) are considered just like other technologies with no role other than their technical role, the view is instrumental. But substantive theorists suggest that ICTs can change the culture of society and their mere existence can make the difference (Macleod, 2005; Ezer, 2006). There is need to consider human diversities "in addition to the technical matters (Walsham, 2000:105)" because if systems are not designed according to the learner perceptions, characteristics (that is, gender, age) and context of use, problems can recur (Graff et al., 2001). Furthermore, if e-Learning matches with the learning style of the learner, the benefits are higher but if otherwise, e-Learning

cannot contribute much (Cagiltay, Yildirim and Aksu, 2006). Aviram and Tami (2004) identify seven approaches (perceptions) and five attitudes (practical behavior) about the development and use of e-Learning, where approaches are: administrative, curricular, didactic, organizational, systemic, cultural and ideological while attitudes have been classified into: agnostic, conservative, moderate, radical and extreme radical.

This research analyses data on the perceptions of students, teachers and administrators in HEIs of North West Frontier Province (NWFP), Pakistan about eLearning development and use. 'Perceptions about the educational technologies' have been used as predictor of the user-perceptions about the development, use, problems and prospects of e-Learning in higher education. Correlation and histograms have been used to test the hypotheses about the 'association' of predictors and criterion variables along with regression analysis to support the relationship between predictor and criterion variables.

LITERATURE REVIEW E-Learning in higher education institutions

E-Learning refers to any level of applying computers and related technologies in pedagogy, learning and education-management (Tinio, 2002; Young, 2003; Gray et al., 2003; Kanuka, 2007). For example, teachers and students in higher education use Internet for browsing, emailing, chatting or any other purpose and thereby learn to add new aspects to their teaching and learning – this is also e-Learning. Similarly, using a computer for preparing lecture (by teacher), an assignment (by student) and typing and composing a letter in the word-editor (by staff) or doing all this virtually as do the virtual universities- all is included in e-Learning (Sife et al., 2007).

The educational use of ICTs is diverse beginning with a simple information delivery (accessing an online library) and stretching to the modern applications of cognitive tools (Web 2.0 technologies), which belong to the family of adaptive and personalization technologies or systems to create individualized learning and teaching environments (Sirkemaa, 2001; Chan and Lee, 2007). ELearning thus, refers to a continuum of educational technologies with Word, Excel, Access and PowerPoint as the main tools on one hand with 'No or little' impact on teaching, learning and administrative practices. On the other divide lies the virtual learning environments using web-based technologies and virtual lecture halls casting wide-spread impacts on pedagogy, learning and educational administration (Sife et al., 2007; Thompson, 2007).

Perceptions about education-technologies

One way to assess a user's approach to e-Learning is the assessment of his/her perceptions and attitudes about the educational technologies because research is documenting individual differences of response to the development and use of e-Learning in HEIs (Graff et al., 2001). The research confirms that the development and use processes of e-Learning can be handled adequately if teachers' perceptions of technology integration and its impact on their instructional practice are well understood beforehand (Zhao and Bryant, 2006) because teachers' attitudes are strongly related to their successful use of new technology (Bataineh and Abdel-Rahman, 2006). Similarly, students' involvement in the use of computers also depends on their perceived usefulness for communication and access to information (Gay et al., 2006). Researchers have grouped e-Learning users, particularly teachers, into:

1. **Cynics:** They have negative perceptions about eLearning but strong pedagogical beliefs therefore unwilling to change.
2. **Moderates:** They like ICTs and ready to change and adapt to new pedagogical practices with some guidance and training.
3. **Adaptors:** These are the intellectual leaders who use e-Learning for inner progress and external enhancements by continuously updating their pedagogy with latest technologies (Mehra and Mital, 2007).

A real big concern in this regard is that the user demographics (age, gender, nationality, learning style), also change the perceptions of an individual, for instance, female users lag behind the male users of educational technologies (Graff et al., 2001). Likewise, Net Genres (new generation of students) have multitasking style, process information differently than their ancestors and better learn in a customizable environments where teachers are no more 'sage on the stage rather guide on the side' (Tinio, 2002; Dinevski and Kokol, 2005). Likewise, younger students have been found less motivated than the older users (Gay et al., 2006). Net Geners bring prior knowledge to the universities, which affect the manner in which students receive, analyze and use the facts and figures (DiCerbo, 2007).

Despite the fact that paradigm shifts in e-Learning have transformed the perceptions of the society about new technologies (Ezziane, 2007), very limited research has been documented about the user perceptions particularly, in the developing countries (Bataineh and AbdelRahman, 2006). A broader grouping of the diversity of perceptions emerges into two wider divisions of theories about the nature and role of education technologies:

1. **Instrumental view:** It is the most commonly held belief that information and communication technologies are a 'tool' without any inherent value rather power lies in the way it is used, thus there can be a 'single-model' for universal application of technologies (Macleod, 2005; Radosevich and Kahn, 2006). Instrumental theory asserts that since education has to serve the society thus focuses should be on the utility of education by enabling the students to apply their knowledge vocationally and contribute to the economy. But, this idea limits the learner to their subjects only thereby blocking their critical thinking about the broader social and communal objectives beyond their professional boundaries (Ezer, 2006).
2. **Substantive view:** Substantive theorists posit that ICTs are not neutral rather determinist and unlike older technologies they have far reaching impacts on the lifestyle of the societies (Young, 2003). This group of perceptions suggests that technology has positive and negative implications for the individuals, groups, organizations and society (Macleod, 2005; Radosevich and Kahn, 2006). The substantive theory matches with the 'liberal theory' of education (Ezer, 2006), which views learning as an active, interconnected and socially collaborative experience and not simply a recollection of facts.

Development of e-Learning

The development of e-Learning environment for HEIs is not automatic rather a complex and multifaceted process that involves, not only technology but also pedagogy, curriculum, institutional e-Readiness, teachers' digital literacy and consistent financing, per se (Tinio, 2002). The growth of innovative practices in e-Learning has developed new skills and novel ways of using them within project

teams for e-Learning projects (Gray et al., 2003). However, the design and development of e-Learning environments must be aligned with the “student requirements (Young, 2003)” In the context of globalization, international connectivity, instant communication through internet and mobile technologies, the universities, all over the world, are confronting huge challenges, both external and internal (Loing, 2005).

A research from universities by Lewis and Goodison (2004), reveals that those who were running successful e-Learning-initiatives, strongly perceived that the “developments needed to be driven by pedagogy, not the technology.” Likewise, data on e-Learning experiences in developed and developing countries provide enough evidence to understand that it is not technology (Jewels and Ford, 2006) rather human and cultural issues which can either work as critical success factors or turn into critical failure variables. For example, culture is a highly influential mediator in the present educational environments wherein pedagogical models are an integral part of the culture of every institute (Nyvang, 2006).

Use of e-Learning

Given the differences of perceptions (Young, 2003) users behave differently while using the e-Learning tools and techniques for teaching, learning and administrative purposes (LaCour, 2005). Moreover, the training that educators do receive does not always match with their educational needs, because the faculty is rarely involved in the decisions about technology and design of new strategies for technology-integration (Juniu, 2005; Zhao and Bryant, 2006). In developing countries, ICTs have not permeated to a great extent in HEIs due to many socio-economic and technological circumstances which hinder the successful use environment (Sife et al., 2007).

The greatest challenge in ‘using’ the e-Learning environments is to adapt the computer-based system to differently skilled learners, for example, if it is too complex, the user will be lost, confused and frustrated but too simple or non-systematic environments can engender problems of user-motivation (Sirkemaa, 2001).

Technology is disruptive by nature, which demands new investments of time, money, space and skills (Aaron et al., 2004). Furthermore, face-to-face communication is critical for classroom social relationships and interpersonal processes, for example, e-Learning have reduced support for social interaction. The emotions can be conveyed through e-mail or chatting but it cannot replace the socio-emotional interaction (Russell, 2005). Taken together, barriers in the use of e-Learning gadgets can make technology use frustrating for the technologically perceptive, let alone the many teachers who may be somewhat techno-phobic (Ezziane, 2007).”

The most troublesome issue in the ‘use’ of e-Learning applications across the HEIs of the developed and developing countries is the provision of sustained technical support by the ICT-professionals and IT-department or division because the success of an e-Learning project is reportedly dependent on the skills and quality of technical support available to the end-users (Gray et al., 2003; Valcke, 2004; Valdez et al., 2004). Juniu (2005) asserts that faculty users do not only depend on ICT staff for technological support but also face pressures from the government, society and pedagogues to use technology in supporting constructive, authentic and cooperative learning. Thus, technology training only cannot

ensure better use of new tools users also need continuous technical and human resource support across the use (Zhao and Bryant, 2006).

Problems of e-Learning

Contemporary research on e-Learning reveals that more than half of all ICT-projects become runways, with overshooting budgets, delayed timetables, escalation in decision making and filing to deliver their objectives (McManus and Wood-Harper, 2004:3; Venables and Tan, 2006). Similarly, though ICTs are emerging in HEIs but the pace and depth of their impact is, “as yet, rather limited (Baumeister, 2006).” Several researchers have identified the problems for the development, use and integration of ICTs into teaching, learning and educational management (Drinkwater et al., 2004; Bondarouk, 2006; Vrana, 2007; Kanuka, 2007; Sife et al., 2007; Wells, 2007):

1. Inertia of behavior of people, like their resistance to changes, etc.
2. Underestimation, lack of awareness and negative attitudes towards ICTs.
3. Lack of systemic approach to implementation and lack of follow-up.
4. High rates of system non-completion.
5. Lack of user-training.
6. Lack of administrative and technical end-user support.
7. User dissatisfaction with new systems.
8. Mismatches between technologies and the context, culture and work practices.

<u>S/n</u>	<u>Variable</u>	<u>Definition</u>
Table 1. Working concepts (extracted variables).		
Code		
1	Perceptions about educational technologies etc., in e-Learning. PET	Views about hardware, software, networking etc., in e-Learning.
2	Perceptions about the development practices	Views about the approaches, methodologies
4	Perceptions about the problems	Problems of educational technologies, development and use of e-Learning.
5	Perceptions about the prospects	Futuristic views of e-Learning and ICT professionals. PRS
	the use practices	Perceived use, ease of use and usability of e-Learning in HEIs. PUP

List of variables (predictor and criterion).

At the broader level, there are development and use problems, which need to be understood and handled at their time of emergence (Gray et al., 2003). Both development and use problems are independent as well as interdependent on each other (Klamma et al., 2007). For example, user participation is important at both the development and use levels of e-Learning environments.

Prospects of e-Learning

As elaborated across the preceding pages, new ICTs are proving something beyond the machine metaphor (Tinio, 2002). These technologies are casting unprecedented impacts on the life of individuals, groups, communities, organizations, societies and the global-village by changing not only

their working patterns but also their culture- the way of life (Sasseville, 2004). Furthermore this is not happening only in the developed countries rather across the globe due to the mass availability of ICTs devices, services, professionalism and knowledge resources (internet with online databases and knowledge resources) (Macleod, 2005).

The most leading and widely recognized and debated aspect of the contemporary ICTs is their potential to provide phenomenal opportunities for the developing countries (Sanyal, 2001; Tinio, 2002; Hvorecký et al., 2005; Sife et al., 2007). Developing states have long been suffering from certain education related problems due to the lack of resources and which seemed insurmountable before the emergence of modern e-Learning tools and techniques (Haddad and Jurich, 2006). For example, the provision of traditional education facilities (schools, colleges, universities decorated with learning services like buildings, furniture, equipments, libraries and so on) for face-to-face education (Hussain, 2007). Following digital opportunities are available to the world communities, particularly, in the countries like Pakistan.

Grounded in the above literature review on the role of user-perceptions about e-Learning, the researcher postulates (hypothesizes) that ‘whatever is the belief (perceptions) of a user about the nature and role of ICTs, the same is translated into action (attitude or physical behavior) towards the development, use, problems and prospects of e-Learning tools and techniques particularly, in the HEIs of NWFP, Pakistan. Thus, ‘perceptions about education technologies’ determine the view and attitudes about all the aspects of e-Learning from development to use (Table 1).

List of hypotheses

1. Predictor is highly correlated with all and each of the criterion variables (H₁, H₂, H₃, H₄, and H₅).
2. PDP depends on the predictor (H₆).
3. PUP is determined by the predictor (H₇).
4. PRB are explained by the predictor (H₈).
5. Predictor determines the PRS (H₉).

RESEARCH DESIGN Approach

There is a huge body of studies in developed and developing countries about the theories and practices of e-Learning in HEIs both from qualitative and quantitative perspectives. The quantitative studies, using survey instruments are multiple and thus very popular method of accessing the problem situation, for example, by Irons et al. (2002), Luck and Norton (2005), Marcella and Knox (2004), Abrami et al. (2006), Johnson et al. (2006), Radosevich and Kahn (2006), Bataineh and AbdelRahman (2006), Thomas and Allen (2006), Mehra and Mital (2007), Martin and Dunsworth (2007), Garcia and Qin (2007), DiCerbo (2007) are some from a list.

Methods

There are twenty one HEIs in NWFP, Pakistan, including universities and other educational institutes. These institutes are offering education in all the subjects of pure and social sciences as well as degrees in computer-literacy. All the university-constituents (students, teachers and administrators) are using computers to their respective levels of computer-proficiency. The ‘Target-Population’ of the project consists of twenty (20) higher education institutions with seventeen (17) universities and three higher

Table 2. Demographic profile of the respondents (n = 354).

City	Male/female	Student	Teacher	Administrator	Total	%age
DIK	Male	31	38	33	102	70.34
	Female	26	17	0	43	29.66
Sub-total		57	55	33	145	40.96
Peshawar	Male	39	49	51	139	66.5
	Female	36	33	1	70	33.5
Total		75	82	52	209	59.04
Grand total		132	137	85	354	100
%age		37.28	38.7	24.02		100

Descriptive statistics.

Table 3. Description of the research variables.

	Min	Max	Mean	Rank	Std. Deviation
PET	3.18	6.55	4.7779	4	0.57637
PDP	3.00	5.89	4.3082	5	0.52236
PUP	3.10	6.75	4.7961	3	0.58463
PRB	3.60	6.34	4.8207	2	0.47971
PRS	2.00	7.00	5.7359	1	0.89704

degree awarding institutes (HEC, 2008) in NWFP, Pakistan. There are about teachers and 7791 administrators in the higher education of NWFP. This paper is a part of the project and includes five variables: one predictor and four criterions, 38 questions excluding demographics of the respondents. Data was analyzed using SPSS 12.0 to create a database, produce the descriptive tables and test the hypothesis. Histograms or scatter plots have been produced to check the linearity and equality of variances between the predictor and dependent variables. The overall reliability of Cronbach’s alpha was estimated at 0.9288, with 354 cases and 38 survey items. This value obviously exceeds the required minimum threshold for the overall Reliability-test, that is, 0.7 (Koo, 2008).

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

Descriptive statistics (Tables 2 and 3)

Testing of hypotheses

H₁: PET is highly correlated with ‘all’ the criterion variables (H₁) Table 4.

The relationship between the predictor and criterion variables is highest in all the analysis. The problems have extreme levels of colinearity and equality of variance with the predictor. The interrelationship is further established by the significance of correlation-analysis (r = 0.834) between the predictor and problems. However, it is very surprising that the prospects of e-Learning are very

insignificantly related with the predictor. Although of 0.455 is significant however, in comparison to other relationships this score is comparatively very low thereby indicating insignificant relationship between the predictor and criterion variable of ‘perceptions about the prospects of e-Learning in HEIs’. Thus, predictor is correlated with all the criterion factors starting from $r = 0.834$ (PRB), to $r = 0.758$ (PDP), $r = 0.746$ (PUP) and ending in $r = 0.455$ (PRS) (Figures 1 to 5).

$H_2, H_3, H_4,$ and H_5 have been explained with the help of correlation-table (Table 4) and scatter diagrams. The first portion has been analyzed above. The scatter diagrams verify the findings of correlations. The thickness of histogram (Figure 4) is highest showing the co-variation of predictor and criterion variable of ‘Problems of eLearning.’ Then come the other relationships in Figures 2, 3 and lastly Figure 4 confirms that the responses are dispersed showing comparatively minimum relationship between the variations of predictor and ‘Prospects of e-Learning.’

H_6 : PDP depends on the predictor (H_6) (Table 5).

H_7 : PUP is determined by the predictor (H_7) (Table 6).

H_8 : PRB are explained by the Predictor (H_8) (Table 7)

H_9 : Predictor determines the PRS (H_9) (Tables 8 and 9)

DISCUSSION

From the above analysis it is evident that most of the

Table 4. Correlation table.

	PET	PDP	PUP	PRB
Perceptions about the educational technologies	0.758 (**)	0.000	0.000	0.000
Perceptions about the development practices	0.746(**) 0.000	0.577(**) 0.000	0.708(**) 0.000	0.431(**) 0.000
Perceptions about the use of practices	0.834(**) 0.000	0.745(**) 0.000	0.708(**) 0.000	0.431(**) 0.000
Perceptions about the e-Learning problems	0.455(**) 0.000	0.334(**) 0.000	0.372(**) 0.000	0.431(**) 0.000
Perceptions about the prospects of e-Learning	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

PREDICTOR OF ELEARNING IN HEIs

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the theoretical framework.

Views about the development practices

Figure 2. Mapping of PDP on PET (H₂).

Opinion about the use practices

Figure 3. Mapping of PUP on PET (H₃).

Perceptions of the eLearning problems

Figure 4. Mapping of PRB on PET (H₄).

Perceptions about the Prospects of eLearning

Figure 5. Mapping of PRS on PET (H₅).

Table 5. Regression of PET on PDP (development).

R	R Square	Adjusted R square	Std. error of the estimate	Fdf=1/352
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Sig.

0.758(a)	0.574	0.573	0.34142	474.306 0.000(a)
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Unstandardized coefficients

Standardized coefficients

	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	1.028	0.152		6.772	0.000
Predictor = PET	0.687	0.032	0.758	21.779	0.000

a. Predictor (perceptions about the educational technologies - PET), b. Dependent variable (PDP).

Table 6. Regression of PET on PUD (use).

R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. Error of the estimate	Fdf=1/352
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Sig.

0.746(a)	0.557	0.555	0.38979	442.074 0.000(a)
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Unstandardized coefficients

Standardized coefficients

	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	1.180	0.173		6.813	0.000
Predictor = PET	0.757	0.036	0.746	21.026	0.000

a. Predictor (perceptions about the educational technologies - PET), b. Dependent variable (PUP).

Table 7. Regression of PET on PRB (problems).

R	R Square	Adjusted R square	Std. error of the estimate	Fdf=1/352
Sig.				
0.834(a)	0.696	0.695	0.26505	804.267 0.000(a)

	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	1.504	0.118		12.770	0.000
Predictor = PET	0.694	0.024	0.834	28.360	0.000

a. Predictor (perceptions about the educational technologies - PET), b. Dependent variable (PeP).

Table 8. Regression of PET on PRS (prospects).

R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. error of the estimate	Fdf=1/352
Sig.				
0.455(a)	0.207	0.204	0.80016	91.661 0.000(a)

	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	2.356	0.356		6.625	0.000
Predictor = PET	0.707	0.074	0.455	9.574	0.000

a. Predictor (perceptions about the educational technologies - PET), b. Dependent variable (PRS).

Dimensions of e-Learning in HEIs are determined by the opinion and attitudes about the development, use, perceptions of e-Learning users about the educational problems and prospects of e-Learning. However, one of technologies themselves. Whatever they perceive about the striking findings is that there is a very nominal and the nature and role of ETS, the same is reflected in their insignificant relationship between the perceptions about ETS and the meaning attached with the prospects of eLearning in the higher education.

As highlighted in the literature, a huge body of research is exploring the impact of user-perceptions and theories on their attitude towards the development, use, problems and future success of e-Learning in the higher education. For example, learners' preferred learning path depends on their personal characteristics like perceptions about technologies and learning styles (Cagiltay et al., 2006). Likewise, teachers' attitudes have been found strongly related to their success in using technology (Bataneh and Abdel-Rahman, 2006). Even in the study of a higher education in England, it was found that in the administration of university, the top-management has different perceptions of education technologies than the lower levels of management (Valcke, 2004). Thus, the individual satisfaction and perception of technologies is closely related to the attitudes of an individual for participating and contributing to the use of e-Learning (Klamma et al., 2007). Therefore, a rigorous research is needed regarding

personal orientations, individual traits and their impacts on the construction of e-Learning environments (Phillips et al., 2008).

Despite the efforts, teacher's ability to integrate technology into teaching and learning is still a big challenge requiring research and investments (Oh and French, 2004). For example, in a study of academicians of higher education in India, the respondents still have the perceptions about technology which are barriers to the successful integration of education technologies in teaching and learning. For example, majority of the respondents perceive technology as more complex and intimidating and required high administrative support (Mehra and Mital, 2007). Thus, successful digital initiatives in higher education are squarely dependent on the change in perceptions of the users about the nature and role of technologies in creating independent and selfregulatory learning in digital environments (Garcia and Qin, 2007).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The problems are very significantly predicted by the perceptions about ETS. Correlation of problems with PET is 0.834 (in both the correlation and regression analysis), the highest in the analysis. Similarly, the histogram (Figure 4) of the same gives a picture where scores of both the variables closely cluster around the regressionline. Furthermore, 70% of variation in the problems is explained by the perceptions about ETS ($R^2 = 0.696$).

Secondly, the development practices are significantly related with PET in all the analysis. $R = 0.758$ and $R^2 = 0.574$ - 58% of variation in development practices is explained by the predictor. Histogram (Figure 1) also creates a view of clustering both the variables around the regression line.

Like PDP, use of the e-Learning is also significantly dependent on the predictor at the third level after problems and development variables. In this relationship, $r = 0.746$, $R^2 = 0.557$ therefore, 56% of the variation in PUP is determined by the predictor. The most insignificant relationship exists between the prospects (PPE) and perceptions about ETS. There is correlation of $r = 0.455$ and $R^2 = 0.207$ therefore only 21% of the changes in prospects are predicted by PET.

Thus, the most thought-provoking finding of the study is that perceptions about educational technologies are responsible for the magnitude of problems. It shows that there is gap between the perceptions and reality. This gap is verified by the higher scores on problems (average = 4.8) and their significant dependence on the perceptions about technologies ($R^2 = 0.696 = 70\%$).

The average score on prospects is the highest (5.7359 in Table 2) but novelty is that this optimism has not been found related with the perceptions of eLearning in the HEIs of the country. There is no or very nominal relationship between the prospects and all other variables as evident from correlation table, histograms and regression analysis. So prospects (expectations) are not stemming from the reality rather hype about the technologies but it is positive and promising. There is need of proper training and education to adjust the perceptions with reality and reality with perceptions.

This study reveals that perceptions about educational technologies are very significantly related with and predict the criterion variable of 'Problems of e-Learning' but surprisingly, the 'prospects of e-Learning' are very nominally associated with and predicted by the predictor. It further points that learners' preferred learning which depends on personal characteristics that is, perceptions about technologies and learning styles, besides strong attitude of teachers' in using technology so, this study suggest to conduct studies by focusing on this aspect in

Table 9. The impacts of predictor (PET) on criterion-variables.

S/n						
3	Perceptions about problems of e-PRB Learning	0.834	0.696	70%		
1	Perceptions about developmentPDP practices	0.758	0.574	58%		
2	Perceptions about use practices PUP	0.746	0.557	56%		
4	Perceptions about prospects of e-PRS Learning	0.455	0.207	21%		

Criterion variables R R2 Volume of prediction

Higher education institutions. Moreover, the administration that is, top and lower management has different perceptions of education technologies, thus, individual satisfaction and perception of technologies is closely related to the attitudes of an individual for participating and contributing to the use of e-Learning so, there is a dire need of conducting a rigorous research for understanding the personal orientations, individual traits and their impacts on the development and promotion of e-Learning environment in HEIs. Though teachers are capable in using and integrating technology in teaching and learning but still it is a big problem which need further investment and research because the misperceptions about technology are still barriers to the successful integration of education technologies in teaching and learning and majority perceive technology as more complex and intimidating that need high administrative support. The successful digital initiatives in higher education institutions depends on the change in perceptions of the users about the nature and role of technologies in creating independent and self-regulatory learning in digital environments.

REFERENCES

- eReforms: PERN, PRR, eLearning, CMS and Digital Library (2008). Higher Education Commission. Retrieved July 14, from <http://www.he European Journal of Open, Distance and E-Learning c.gov.pk/new/eReforms/eReforms.htm>.
- Aaron M, Dicks D, Ives C, Montgomery B (2004). Planning for Integrating Teaching Technologies. spring. Retrieved May 14, 2007, from <http://www.cjlt.ca/>. Can. J. Learn. Technol., 30: 2.
- Abrami PC, Bernard RM, Wade A, Schmid RF, Borokhovski E, Tamim R, Surkes MA, Lowerison G, Zhang D, Nicolaidou I, Newman S, Wozney I, Peretiatkowicz A (2006). A Review of e-Learning in Canada: A Rough Sketch of the Evidence, Gaps and Promising Directions. Fall/Autumn. Retrieved May 14, 2007, from <http://www.cjlt.ca/>. Can. J. Learn. Technol., 32: 3.
- Aviram R, Tami D (2004). The impact of ICT on education: the three opposed paradigms, the lacking discourse. Retrieved July 14, 2007, from http://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/~mueller/kr-004/ressources/ict_impact.pdf.

- Bataineh RF, Abdel-Rahman AA (2006). Jordanian EFL students' perceptions of their computer literacy: An exploratory case study. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://ijedict.dec.uwi.edu//viewarticle.php?id=169&layout=html>]. *Int. J. Educ. Develop. Using ICT*, 2: 2.
- Baumeister H (2006). Networked Learning in the Knowledge Economy - A Systemic Challenge for Universities. *Eur. J. Open, Distance ELearning*. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://www.eurodl.org/>.
- Bondarouk TV (2006). Action-oriented group learning in the implementation of information technologies: results from three case studies. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://www.palgravejournals.com/ejis/>. *Eur. J. Inf. Sys.*, 15: 42–53.
- Cagiltay NE, Yildirim S, Aksu M (2006). Students' Preferences on WebBased Instruction: linear or non-linear. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://www.ask4research.info/> *J. Educ. Technol. Soc.*, 9(3): 122-136.
- Chan A, Lee MJW (2007). We want to be Teachers, Not Programmers: In Pursuit of Relevance and Authenticity for Initial Teacher Education Students Studying an Information Technology Subject at an Australian University. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://ejite.isu.edu/> 3:1. *Elect J. Integr. Technol. Educ.*, 6: 79.
- DiCerbo KE (2007). Knowledge Structures of Entering Computer Networking Students and Their Instructors. Retrieved July 14, 2007, from <http://jite.org/documents/> Dinevski D, Kokol DP (2005). ICT and Lifelong Learning. *European Journal of Open, Distance and E-Learning*. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://www.eurodl.org/>. Drinkwater PMmailto:p.drinkwater@mbs.ac.uk, Adelinemailto:Christine@vcsinet.com CM, French S, Papamichailmailto:n.papmichail@mbs.ac.uk KN, Rickards T (2004). mailto:t.rickards@mbs.ac.uk Adopting a Web-Based Collaborative Tool to Support The Manchester Method Approach to Learning. Retrieved April 19, 2007 from <http://www.ejel.org/volume-2/vol2issue1/issue1-art23-drinkwater.pdf>. *Elect. J. E-Learn.*, 2(1): 61-68.
- Ezer J (2006). India and the USA: A Comparison through the Lens of Model IT Curricula. Retrieved July 14, 2007, from <http://jite.org/documents/Vol5/>. *J. Inf. Technol. Educ.*, Vol. 5.
- Ezziane Z (2007) Information Technology Literacy: Implications on Teaching and Learning. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://www.ask4research.info/>. *J. Educ. Technol. Soc.*, 10(3): 175191.

- Garcia P, Qin J (2007). Identifying the Generation Gap in Higher Education: Where Do the Differences Really Lie? *Innovate* April/May. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://Innovateonline.info>. *J. Online Educ.*, 3: 4.
- Gay G, Mahon S, Devonish D, Alleyne, P, Alleyne PG (2006). Perceptions of information and communication technology among undergraduate management students in Barbados. *Intern. J. Educ. Dev., Using ICT*, 2: 4. Retrieved May 11, 2007, from <http://ijedict.dec.uwi.edu/>.
- Graff M, Davies J, McNorton M (2001). Cognitive Style and Cross Cultural Differences in Internet Use and Computer Attitudes. *European Journal of Open, Distance and E-Learning*. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://www.eurodl.org/>.
- Gray DE, Ryan M, Coulon A (2003). The Training of Teachers and Trainers: Innovative Practices, Skills and Competencies in the use of eLearning. *Eur. J. Open, Dist. E-Learn*. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://www.eurodl.org/>.
- Haddad WD, Jurich S (2006). ICT for education: Potential and potency.
- UNESCO. Retrieved July 14, 2007, from http://web2.iastate.edu/~ilet/reading_groups/Pdf_files/o3UNESCO.pdf.
- Hussain DI (2007). Transnational education: Concept and methods. January. Retrieved July 14, 2007, *Turk. Online J. Dist. Educ.*, 8(1): 13,
- Hvorecký J, Manažmentu VS, Cesta P (2005). Can E-learning break the Digital Divide? *European Journal Open, Distance and E-Learning*. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://www.eurodl.org/>.
- Irons LR, Jung DJ, Keel RO (2002). Interactivity in Distance Learning: The Digital Divide and Student Satisfaction. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://www.ask4research.info/>. *J. Educ. Technol. Soc.*, 5: 3.
- Jewels T, Ford M (2006). The Development of a Taxonomy of Desired Personal Qualities for IT Project Team Members and Its Use in an Educational Setting. Retrieved July 14, 2007, from <http://jite.org/documents/Vol5/>. *J. Info. Technol., Educ.*, Vol. 5.
- Johnson DW, Bartholomew KW, Miller D (2006). Improving Computer Literacy of Business Management Majors: A Case Study Retrieved July 14, 2007, from <http://jite.org/documents/Vol5/>. *J. Inf. Technol. Educ.*, Vol. 5.
- Juniu S (2005). Digital Democracy in Higher Education Bridging the Digital Divide. October/November. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://Innovateonline.info>. *Inf. Innov. J. Online Educ.*, 2(1).

- Kanuka H (2007). Instructional Design and eLearning: A Discussion of Pedagogical Content Knowledge as a Missing Construct. e- Retrieved July 18, 2007, from http://www.usq.edu.au/electpub/ejist/docs/vol9_no2/default.htm. *J. Instruct. Sci. Technol., (e-JIST)*. 9: 2.
- Klamma R, Chatti MA, Duval E, Hummel H, Hvannberg EH, Kravcik M, Law E, Naeve A, Scott P (2007). Social Software for Life-long Learning. Retrieved June 24, 2007, from <http://www.ask4research.info/>. *J. Educ.Technol. Soc.*, 10(3): 72-83.
- Koo AC (2008). Factors affecting teachers' perceived readiness for online collaborative learning: A case study in Malaysia. Retrieved November 10, 2008, from <http://www.ask4research.info/> *J. Educ .Technol. Soc.*, 11(1): 266-278.
- LaCour S (2005). The future of integration, personalization, and ePortfolio technologies. April/May. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://Innovateonline.info>. *Innovate J. Online Educ.*, 1: 4.
- Lewis D, Goodison R (2004). Enhancing learning with Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Higher Education. Research Report RR533, Department for Education and Skills. © University of Wolverhampton 2004, ISBN 1 84478 225 5. Retrieved July 14, 2007, from <http://www.dfes.gov.uk/research/data/uploadfiles/RR533.pdf>.
- Loing B (2005). ICT and Higher Education. General delegate of ICDE at UNESCO. 9th UNESCO/NGO Collective Consultation on Higher Education (6-8 April). Retrieved June 24, 2007, from <http://ongcomite-liaison.unesco.org/ongpho/acti/3/11/rendu/20/pdfen.pdf>.
- Luck P, Norton B (2005). Problem Based Management Learning-Better Online? *Eur. J. Open, Dist. E-Learn*. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://www.eurodl.org/>.
- Macleod H (2005). What role can educational multimedia play in narrowing the digital divide? Retrieved May 11, 2007, from <http://ijedict.dec.uwi.edu/>. *Int. J. Educ. Dev., Using ICT*, 1: 4.
- Marcella R, Knox K (2004). Systems for the management of information in a university context: An investigation of user need. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://InformationR.net/ir/9-2/paper172.html>. *Inf. Res.*, 9(2): 172.
- Martin F, Dunsworth Q (2007). A Methodical Formative Evaluation of Computer Literacy Course: What and How to Teach. Retrieved October 10, 2007, from <http://jite.org/documents/Vol6/>. *J. Inf. Technol. Educ.*, Vol. 6.

- McManus J, Wood-Harper T (2004). Information systems project management: Methods, tools and techniques. Pearson Education, Limited, UK.
- Mehra P, Mital M (2007). Integrating technology into the teaching/learning transaction: Pedagogical and technological perceptions of management faculty. Retrieved October 11, 2007, from <http://ijedict.dec.uwi.edu/>. Int. J. Educ. Dev. Using ICT, 3: 1.
- Nyvang T (2006). Implementation of ICT in Higher Education as Interacting Activity Systems. Retrieved June 24, 2007 networkedlearningconference.org.uk/abstracts/pdfs/P27%20Nyvang.pdf.
- Oh E, French DR (2004). Pre-service Teachers' Perceptions of an Introductory Instructional Technology Course. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://ejite.isu.edu/> 3:1. Elect. J. Integrat. Technol. Educ., 3: 1.
- Phillips P, Wells J, Ice P, Curtis R, Kennedy R (2008). A Case Study of the Relationship Between Socio-Epistemological Teaching Orientations and Instructor Perceptions of Pedagogy in Online Environments. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://ejite.isu.edu/Volume6No1/>. Elect. J. Integr. Technol. Educ., 6: 3-27.
- Radosevich D, Kahn P (2006). Using Tablet Technology and Recording Software to Enhance Pedagogy. Aug/Sep. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://Innovateonline.info>. Innov. J. Online Educ., 2: 6.
- Russell G (2005). The Distancing Question in Online Education. April/May. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://Innovateonline.info>. Innovate J. Online Educ., 1: 4.
- Sanyal BC (2001). New functions of higher education and ICT to achieve education for all. Expert Roundtable on University and Technology-for-Literacy/Basic Education Partnership in Developing Countries. Paris, 10 to 12 Sep, 2001. International Institute for Educational Planning, UNESCO. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://www.literacyonline.org/products/ili/pdf/UTLPsanyal.pdf>. Sasseville B (2004). Integrating Information and Communication Technology in the Classroom: A Comparative Discourse Analysis. Spring. Retrieved May 14, 2007, from <http://www.cjlt.ca/>. Can. J. Learn. Technol., 30: 2.
- Sife AS, Lwoga ET, Sanga C (2007). New technologies for teaching and learning: Challenges for higher learning institutions in developing countries. Retrieved July 21, from <http://ijedict.dec.uwi.edu/>. Int. J. Educ. Dev. Using ICT, 3: 1.

- Sirkemaa S (2001). Information technology in developing a metalearning environment. Eur. J. Open, Dist. E-Learn. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://www.eurodl.org/>.
- Thomas T, Allen A (2006). Gender Differences in Students' Perceptions of Information Technology as a Career. Retrieved July 14, 2007, from <http://jite.org/documents/Vol5/>. J. Inf. Technol. Educ., Vol. 5.
- Thompson J (2007). Is Education 1.0 Ready for Web 2.0 Students? April/May. Retrieved October 22, 2007, from <http://Innovateonline.info>. Innov. J. Online Educ., 3: 4.
- Tinio VL (2002). ICT in education. Presented by UNDP for the benefit of participants to the World Summit on the Information Society. UNDP's regional project, the Asia-Pacific Development Information Program (APDIP), in association with the secretariat of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN). Retrieved July 14, 2007 from <http://www.apdip.net/publications/iespprimers/eprimer-edu.pdf>.
- Valcke M (2004). ICT in higher education: An uncomfortable zone for institutes and their policies. In R. Atkinson, C. McBeath, D. JonasDwyer and R. Phillips (Eds), Beyond the comfort zone: Proceedings of the 21st ASCILITE Conference. Perth, 5-8 December. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://www.ascilite.org.au/conferences/perth04/procs/valckekeynote.html>, pp. 20-35.
- Valdez G, Fulton K, Glenn A, Wimmer NA, Blomeyer R (2004). Effective Technology Integration in Teacher Education: A Comparative Study of Six Programs. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://Innovateonline.info>. Innov. J. Online Educ., 1: 1.
- Venables A, Tan G (2006). Thinking and Behaving Scientifically in Computer Science: When Failure is an Option! Retrieved July 14, 2007, from <http://jite.org/documents/Vol5/>. J. Inf. Technol. Educ., Vol. 5.
- Vrana I (2007). Changes required by ICT era are painful sometimes. CAUSE98, an EDUCAUSE conference, online proceedings. Retrieved October 10, 2007, from <http://www.educause.edu/copyright.html>.
- Walsham G (2000). IT/S in developing countries. In: Zeleny, Milan (editor) The IEIBM handbook of information technology in business. Business Press, Thomson Learning. Pp. 105-109.
- Wells R (2007). Challenges and opportunities in ICT educational development: A Ugandan case study. Retrieved July 21, 2007 from <http://ijedict.dec.uwi.edu/>. Int. J. Educ. Dev. Using ICT, 3: 2.

- Young LD (2003). Bridging Theory and Practice: Developing Guidelines to Facilitate the Design of Computer-based Learning Environments. Fall/Autumn. Retrieved May 14, 2007, from <http://www.cjlt.ca/>. Can. J. Learn. Technol., 29: 3.
- Zhao Y, LeAnna Bryant F (2006). Can Teacher Technology Integration Training Alone Lead to High Levels of Technology Integration? A Qualitative Look at Teachers' Technology Integration after State Mandated Technology Training. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <[http://ejite.isu.edu/5\(1\)](http://ejite.isu.edu/5(1))>. Elect. J. Integr. Technol. Educ., 5: 53-62.